

Solvothermal modification of activated carbon for enhanced electrochemical performance in screen-printed supercapacitors

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HIGHLIGHTS

- DMF is incorporated within YP-80F activated carbon using solvothermal treatment.
- Treatment improves hydrophilicity, ink stability, and active surface area.
- Specific capacitance is increased by 80 % (DES)/140 % (aqueous).
- Solvothermal modification does not impact cyclic stability.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

This study reports a novel method for enhancing the specific capacitance of screen-printed, activated-carbon-based supercapacitor electrodes through solvothermal modification of the active material. Commercial activated carbon (Kuraray YP-80F) is suspended in N,N-Dimethylformamide (DMF) and heat treated in a sealed autoclave at 160 °C for 12 h to modify its hydrophilicity and surface properties, eliminating the need for an additional drying retardant in the aqueous electrode ink that limits its electrochemically active surface area. Additionally, the average pore volume of the carbon material is increased by 50 % ($1.22 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$ to $1.83 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$) and the specific surface area by 21 % ($2040 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ to $2471 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$), resulting in further enhanced double layer formation. Screen-printed two-electrode supercapacitors demonstrate a specific capacitance increase of $\sim 140 \%$ (12 F g^{-1} to 28 F g^{-1}) with aqueous electrolyte, and $\sim 80 \%$ (18 F g^{-1} to 33 F g^{-1}) with deep eutectic solvent (DES) electrolyte, compared to cells fabricated using a commercial drying retardant. Moreover, similar capacitance retention after 10,000 charge-discharge cycles ($\sim 95 \%$ with aqueous, $\sim 85 \%$ with DES), and a 22–25 % reduction in

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capacitance-normalised leakage current ($40 \mu\text{A F}^{-1}$ to $30 \mu\text{A F}^{-1}$ with aqueous, $145 \mu\text{A F}^{-1}$ to $113 \mu\text{A F}^{-1}$ with DES) is obtained using solvothermal treatment.

1. Introduction

Printed supercapacitors (SCs) provide electrical energy storage for thin, flexible, and wearable electronic devices [1–5]. Due to their electrostatic charge storage process based on the capacitance of the electrochemical double layer, they exhibit long cycle life, excellent safety and stability, and fast charging and discharging capability to quickly accept and deliver electrical energy [6,7]. Combining SCs with energy harvesters such as triboelectric nanogenerators can provide sustained operation for low-power devices, including wireless sensors for industrial, environmental, and medical monitoring applications [8–15].

The common type of SC is the electrochemical double layer capacitor (EDLC), which utilises high specific surface area (SSA) carbon as its active material to achieve its high specific capacitance. The most widely employed EDLC-type material by far is activated carbon, which has an SSA of $\sim 2000 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$ as measured with the Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method. Activated carbon can be easily synthesised from renewable bio-based precursors, such as wood or coconut shells, making it abundant and inexpensive [16–18]. Other high-SSA carbon materials have also been demonstrated, including graphene [19–21], carbon nanotubes [22–24], carbide-derived-carbon [25,26], carbon nanofibres [27,28], and carbon nanoflakes [29,30]; however, their bulk synthesis is considerably more expensive compared to activated carbon. Pseudocapacitive compounds, which primarily store energy through reversible faradaic reactions, can be used to increase the apparent specific capacitance of the active material beyond the capacitance of the double layer [31]. The most extensively studied pseudocapacitive materials include transition metal oxides [32] such as RuO_2 [33–36], MnO_2 [37,38], and SnO_2 [39–41], and conductive polymers such as PANI [42,43] and PPy [44,45]; however, they generally suffer from inferior cyclic stability and power density compared to EDLC-type materials [46].

Printing techniques such as screen-printing, gravure printing, and flexographic printing enable high-throughput and cost-effective fabrication on thin and flexible substrates, including plastic and biopolymeric films [1,47]. Areal specific capacitance values obtained in various printed activated-carbon-based SCs are presented in Table 1. Among the aforementioned techniques, screen-printing is a particularly attractive fabrication process for stacked SCs, as it can produce thick and large layers required for the fabrication of high-capacitance electrodes. However, ink formulation presents a significant challenge in terms of electrochemical performance and material compatibility, due to the ink's constant atmospheric exposure during printing [48]. As the ink is spread into a thin layer on the mesh surface prior to deposition, a quick drying rate can easily cause the mesh openings to get clogged, preventing good print quality and consistent electrical performance. This is particularly a challenge associated with aqueous inks due to the high volatility of the liquid medium, and the high specific surface area of

activated carbon can further accelerate the evaporation process. For this reason, additives are employed to slow down the drying rate, as well as to improve the wettability and homogeneity of the ink [49].

In a recent publication [50] we reported the development of monolithically stacked screen-printed SCs using commercial activated carbon (Kuraray YP-80F) as the electrode material. A low-cost and environmentally benign activated carbon (AC) ink with water as the suspending medium was synthesised to fabricate the SC electrodes. To achieve sufficient printability for the ink, commercially available drying retardant designed for screen-printing (EPTAINKS Texilac Ritardante) was added to the ink mixture. However, this adversely impacts the specific capacitance of the printed electrodes, due to parts of the microporous carbon matrix becoming inaccessible for the electrolyte. In this study, a method for improving the printability of the carbon ink without the use of drying retardant is presented, resulting in significantly enhanced electrochemical performance. Probe sonication and solvothermal treatment are used to incorporate N,N-Dimethylformamide (DMF) within the porous carbon matrix, which improves the printability and stability of the aqueous ink. During probe sonication and thermal treatment in DMF, the solvent not only facilitates the dispersion of activated carbon particles, but also significantly alters the surface chemistry of the material. According to work reported by Li et al. 2019 [51], DMF, due to its polarity, facilitates the surface modification of carbon nanospheres, significantly enhancing the incorporation of oxygen-containing functional groups and improving their adsorption performance. In addition, DMF treatment can shift the surface potential of carbon nanospheres from negative to positive, which enhances their selectivity toward anionic or cationic molecules [51]. These surface modifications arise from the solvent's strong solvating power, which disrupts the carbon-carbon bonds on the particle surface, enabling the attachment of these functional groups. The introduction of these functional groups enhances the hydrophilicity of the activated carbon, thereby improving its compatibility with aqueous or polar media. This increased hydrophilicity enhances the ink's interaction with substrates and improves the wetting properties during the printing process, which is essential for achieving robust adhesion and uniform deposition in screen printing. Additionally, the functional groups contribute to the improved dispersion of activated carbon particles in the DMF solution, resulting in a more stable ink formulation that can be printed effectively without the need for additional drying retardants. Thus, DMF treatment not only modifies the surface properties of activated carbon, but also optimises its characteristics for energy storage applications, ensuring superior printability and enhanced electrochemical performance.

Table 1
Comparison of printed activated-carbon-based supercapacitors.

Electrodes	Printing technique	Electrolyte	Supercapacitor structure	Specific capacitance	Reference
Activated carbon + Super-P	Blade coating	PVA/ H_3PO_4	Stacked	45 mF cm^{-2} at 0.3 mA cm^{-2}	[52]
Activated carbon	Inkjet printing	$1 \text{ M Et}_4\text{NBF}_4$ /anhydrous propylene carbonate	Interdigital	2.1 mF cm^{-2} at 1 mV s^{-1}	[53]
Activated carbon + Super-P	Direct ink writing	$1 \text{ M Na}_2\text{SO}_4$ in Na CMC	Interdigital and stacked	27.3 mF cm^{-2} (interdigital), 49.4 mF cm^{-2} (stacked) at 5 mV s^{-1}	[54]
Activated carbon	Screen printing	1 M NaCl	Stacked	$110\text{--}200 \text{ mF cm}^{-2}$ at 0.56 mA cm^{-2}	[55]
Activated carbon	Screen printing	NaCl	Stacked	43 mF cm^{-2} at 0.3 mA cm^{-2}	[50]
Activated carbon	Screen printing	3.4 M NaCl	Stacked	94 mF cm^{-2} at 0.15 A g^{-1}	This work

Fig. 1. Structure of the screen-printed supercapacitor test cell.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

Activated carbon powder (YP-80F) was procured from Kuraray Chemical Co., Japan. Choline chloride, sodium chloride, urea, N, N-dimethylformamide (DMF, 99.5 %), and chitosan derived from shrimp shells (product no. 50494) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. All reagents were used without further purification, and Milli-Q deionised water (Millipore, Merck) was employed throughout the experiments. A commercially available drying retardant (EPTAINKS Texilac Ritardante) was used for the fabrication of non-treated AC electrodes. Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) film (125 μm , Melinex ST506, DuPont Teijin Films) was used as a substrate for the printed SCs. Graphite paste (LOCTITE EDAG PF 407C E&C) was used for fabricating the current collectors, and Dynacap GT 0.45/40 cellulose membrane from Glatfelter was used as the separator material. Adhesive from 3M (468 MP) was used for sealing the printed SCs.

2.2. Solvothermal synthesis of treated activated carbon (TAC)

Treated activated carbon (TAC) was prepared via a solvothermal method. Initially, 10 g of activated carbon was dispersed in 60 ml of DMF at ambient temperature using an ultrasonic processor (UP200St, Hielscher Ultrasonics GmbH) to achieve a stable and uniform suspension. The resulting homogeneous mixture was then transferred to a 125 ml Teflon-lined autoclave (Model 4748, Parr Instrument Company, USA) and subjected to solvothermal treatment at temperatures ranging from 160 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 180 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for varied durations of 6, 12, and 24 h. After cooling, the product was repeatedly washed with deionised water until the pH of the filtrate reached neutral, ensuring the removal of any unreacted species. The final powder was then dried in a hot air oven at 90 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 12 h to obtain the TAC active material.

2.3. Electrode ink preparation

Electrode inks with and without drying retardant were prepared for the fabrication of treated (TAC) and non-treated (AC) activated carbon electrodes. A binder solution was first prepared by combining 2.45 wt% of chitosan, 1.01 wt% of acetic acid, and 96.54 wt% of deionised water in a 100 ml glass bottle and mixing the ingredients with a magnetic stirrer, until a homogeneous solution was obtained. TAC ink was prepared by mixing 58 wt% of chitosan solution, 26 wt% of active material, and 16 wt% of water, while AC ink was prepared by mixing 43 wt% of chitosan solution, 20 wt% of active material, 12 wt% of water, and 25 wt% of Texilac drying retardant, as described in previous work [50].

2.4. Preparation of aqueous and deep eutectic solvent (DES) electrolytes

Aqueous (NaCl) and Reline (DES) solutions were prepared and used as electrolytes for the fabricated SCs. The aqueous electrolyte was prepared by dissolving sodium chloride salt to room-temperature deionised water in a 3.4 M concentration. The DES electrolyte was prepared by mixing choline chloride salt and urea in a 1:2 M ratio; the mixture was heated to 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with continuous stirring (VMS C7 Advanced, VWR) until a clear, homogeneous liquid formed. Once cooled to room temperature, this liquid was used as the electrolyte for the DES-based SCs.

2.5. Supercapacitor fabrication

Symmetric test cells with a stacked structure (Fig. 1) were fabricated on PET substrate. The current collector ($x = 34$ mm, $y = 31$ mm, $z \approx 20$ μm) and electrode ($x = 33$ mm, $y = 10$ mm, $z \approx 20$ μm) layers were consecutively screen-printed using an Ekra X5 Professional flatbed printer, and oven cured at 95 $^{\circ}\text{C}/60$ min and 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}/30$ min, respectively. Printing speed of 20 mm s^{-1} , snap-off of 2.00 mm, squeegee angle of 60 $^{\circ}$, and downward force of 200 N was used for the printing process. Polyester mesh with a thread diameter of 125 μm and a mesh count of 24 cm^{-1} was employed for the current collector screen, and polyester mesh with a thread diameter of 55 μm and a mesh count of 48 cm^{-1} for the electrode screen, resulting in electrodes with an approximate thickness of 20 μm and a total mass of 6 mg. After printing the electrode and current collector layers, approximately 100 μl of electrolyte was applied on each electrode, and a separator ($x = 40$ mm, $y = 20$ mm, $z \approx 20$ μm) was sandwiched between the electrodes before sealing the device with adhesive.

2.6. Material characterisation

The specific surface area and pore size distribution of non-treated AC and TAC was evaluated using nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms at 77 K. Measurements were conducted with a 3Flex surface characterisation analyser (Micromeritics Instrument Corporation, USA). Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method was applied to determine the surface area, while the pore size distribution was derived from the adsorption and desorption data. Thermal stability of AC and TAC samples was examined using a TGA-Q500 thermal analyser (TA Instruments, USA). The samples were heated from 30 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 790 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to record their weight loss profiles throughout the temperature range. TGA was performed using a 40:60 nitrogen-to-air mixture; this controlled atmosphere helps slow down the oxidation process and prevents rapid or complete combustion. ^1H NMR analysis was carried out on an NMR spectrometer (SCZ500R, JEOL Resonance, Japan). FTIR spectra were collected using the ATR method on a PerkinElmer Spectrum One spectrophotometer (PerkinElmer, Waltham, MA). Dried powder samples were pressed onto the ATR crystal, with spectra recorded at 4 cm^{-1} resolution, averaged over 32 scans from 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} . Raman analysis of both AC and TAC was performed using a Renishaw inVia Qontor Raman spectrometer coupled with a confocal microscope and equipped with a 50 \times objective lens. The samples were excited with a 532 nm diode-pumped solid-state laser operating at 30 mW. Spectra were acquired by averaging five individual measurements, each with an integration time of 30 s, over the spectral range of 100–3200 cm^{-1} . X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of AC and TAC samples were obtained using a Panalytical Empyrean multipurpose diffractometer. Morphology characterization of the samples was performed using a Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM, JEOL JEM-F200) and a Zeiss Ultraplus Field-Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FESEM). For TEM sample preparation, the powdered material was gently ground between glass slides, dispersed in isopropanol, and drop-cast onto a copper grid coated with holey carbon. For FESEM imaging and elemental analysis by

Fig. 2. Electrodes screen-printed on top of graphite current collectors, with no drying retardant added to the ink mixture, using (a) non-treated AC, and (b) TAC treated at 160 °C for 12 h as the active material. Contact angle measurements of (c) AC and (d) TAC inks on graphite surface.

energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), the samples were cut into pieces of approximately 7 × 7 mm and mounted on aluminum stubs (Agar, AGG301F) using conductive carbon adhesive discs (Agar, AGG3347N). To improve electrical grounding and minimize charging during imaging, conductive carbon glue (Agar, AG16050) was applied between the sample edge and the stub. Then, a thin carbon layer (~10 nm) was deposited onto the sample surface using a high-vacuum sputter coater (Leica EM ACE600) via carbon thread pulses. Surface morphology of both AC and TAC samples was examined using a Zeiss Ultra Plus FESEM operated at an accelerating voltage of 10 kV and a working distance of 8.3 mm. Elemental mapping analysis was performed with the FESEM-integrated Oxford Instruments X-MaxN EDS detector.

2.7. Electrochemical characterisation

The electrochemical performance of each two-electrode SC was characterised using galvanostatic charge/discharge (GCD), cyclic voltammetry (CV), and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS). GCD and CV measurements were performed at current densities of 0.15, 0.5, and 1.5 A g⁻¹ and scan rates of 5, 10, 50, and 100 mV s⁻¹, respectively, using a programmable galvanostat/potentiostat (Maccor 4300). The aqueous and DES-based SCs were characterised using voltage windows of 0–1.2 V and 0–1.8 V, respectively. The gravimetric CV-capacitance was calculated according to equation

$$C_S = \frac{\int_0^{2V_0/\nu} I(t) dt}{m2V_0} \quad (1)$$

where $I(t)$ is the measured electric current as a function of time, V_0 is the maximum voltage used for the measurement, ν is the scan rate, and m is the combined mass of the two electrodes. The GCD-capacitance was determined from the discharge curve between 80 % and 40 % of the maximum voltage, according to equation

$$C_S = \frac{I\Delta t}{m\Delta V} \quad (2)$$

where I is the constant discharge current, Δt is the discharge time, ΔV is the corresponding voltage difference, and m is the combined mass of the two electrodes. ESR was determined from the initial voltage drop of a 1.5 A g⁻¹ constant current discharge as per equation

$$ESR = \frac{V_{drop}}{\Delta I} \quad (3)$$

where V_{drop} is the instantaneous voltage drop caused by the change in current ΔI . The energy density of each SC was calculated according to equation

$$ED = \frac{C_S \cdot V_0^2}{2} \quad (4)$$

where C_S is the specific capacitance measured at 0.15 A g⁻¹. The maximum power density was calculated using equation

$$PD_{max} = \frac{V_0^2}{4 \cdot ESR \cdot m} \quad (5)$$

where PD_{max} describes the theoretical maximum power delivered to a resistive load equal to the ESR of the SC [56]. The average discharge power density was calculated according to equation

$$PD_{avg} = \frac{ED}{t_d} \quad (6)$$

where t_d is the discharge time [57]. Leakage current was determined by holding the SC at its maximum voltage for 1 h, and measuring the required charging current at the end of the holding period.

A Zahner Zennium potentiostat was used to carry out EIS measurements for the two-electrode SCs, as well as three-electrode CV measurements for the screen-printed AC and TAC electrodes. EIS measurements were performed at open-circuit potential, in a frequency range of 10 mHz–1 MHz. Three-electrode CV measurements were performed in aqueous NaCl electrolyte, using an Ag/AgCl reference electrode and a coiled platinum wire counter electrode. Cyclic voltammograms were recorded in a potential window of 0–1 V vs. Ag/AgCl, at scan rates of 2, 5, 8, 10, 15, 20, and 30 mV s⁻¹.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Printability and solvothermal process optimisation

Solvothermal modification substantially improved the screen-printability of the activated carbon material, allowing the deposition

Fig. 3. (a) (a) N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms with insets highlighting the zoomed-in view of the relative pressure range ($p/p^0 = 0.5-1.0$) for both adsorption and desorption, (b) Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) pore size distribution, (c) TGA curve, and (d) 1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO-d₆) spectra of AC and TAC electrode materials.

of uniform TAC electrodes without the addition of any drying retardant to the ink mixture (Fig. 2b). Conversely, non-treated AC was not printable with the same ink formulation (Fig. 2a) due to rapid drying within the openings of the mesh, thus requiring the addition of Texilac for proper deposition. Contact angle measurements revealed an improvement in wetting as a result of solvothermal treatment, with AC (without Texilac) and TAC inks demonstrating contact angles of $\sim 90^\circ$ and $\sim 60^\circ$, respectively (Fig. 2c and d). The printed electrodes also demonstrated high wetting compatibility with the electrolytes; DES demonstrated contact angles of $\sim 15^\circ$ on AC and $\sim 11^\circ$ on TAC, while NaCl demonstrated near-perfect wetting on both surfaces (Fig. S1 in supplementary information), indicating good electrolyte accessibility.

Rheological characterization of the inks was performed at room temperature using a rotational rheometer (DHR-2, TA Instruments Inc., USA) fitted with a 20 mm parallel plate configuration. Apparent viscosity was recorded over a shear rate range of $0.1-500 \text{ s}^{-1}$ to assess flow behaviour. Shear modulus measurements were recorded over a frequency range of $1-100 \text{ rad s}^{-1}$ for the determination of the storage modulus (G') and loss modulus (G''). The obtained results are displayed in Fig. S2 of supplementary information. The measurements demonstrate that TAC and AC inks with and without Texilac exhibit pronounced shear-thinning behaviour. At low shear rates (0.1 s^{-1}), TAC maintains a viscosity of 600 Pa s compared to 1361 Pa s for AC, indicating better flow control while still providing adequate shape retention at rest. Under printing conditions (100 s^{-1}), TAC ink viscosity decreases dramatically to 6 Pa s , enabling effortless flow through screen mesh.

This 100-fold viscosity reduction represents optimal shear-thinning characteristics essential for high-quality screen-printing applications. Additionally, the dynamic measurements confirm optimal gel-like behaviour, as the storage modulus (G') is consistently higher than loss modulus (G'') across all frequencies, demonstrating that the inks maintain a strong, gel-like network and structural resilience under oscillatory stress. When compared with control formulations, the AC formulation shows higher initial viscosity (800 Pa s) but insufficient shear-thinning characteristics, while AC with Texilac exhibits lower overall viscosity. In contrast, the TAC formulation achieves the optimal balance of high rest viscosity for pattern definition and low processing viscosity for efficient printing. This shear-thinning profile is ideally suited for screen printing applications, matching the characteristics reported for successful multi-conductive inks [32].

To optimise the solvothermal process used for the synthesis of TAC, treatment temperature was varied between 160°C and 180°C and treatment time between 6, 12, and 24 h. Initially, solvothermal treatment in DMF was carried out at 180°C temperature, and the effect of treatment time on printing quality was visually observed. The shortest treatment time of 6 h was deemed inadequate for achieving high-quality deposition, while both 12 h and 24 h treatment times yielded high printing quality and similar overall electrochemical performance in symmetric aqueous SCs. Similar results were obtained when lowering the process temperature to 160°C . The most consistent electrode deposition was obtained with TAC treated at 160°C for 12 h, yielding an average mass loading of $836 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ with a standard deviation of $35 \mu\text{g}$

Fig. 4. (a) Raman, (b) FTIR, and (c) XRD of AC and TAC. (d) EDS spectra of pristine AC sample. N content is 12.0 wt% (σ). (e) EDS spectra of TAC sample. N content is 31.4 wt% (σ). Elemental mapping analysis of TAC: (f) EDS layered image, (g) carbon distribution, (h) oxygen distribution, and (i) nitrogen distribution.

cm^{-2} (4.2 %). This variant of TAC yielded a single-electrode areal specific capacitance of $\sim 94 \text{ mF cm}^{-2}$ at 0.15 A g^{-1} with the aqueous electrolyte and was used for the remaining material and electrochemical characterisations. Although no significant differences in electrochemical performance were observed between different TAC variants, the solvothermal process could be further optimised to reduce the treatment time and temperature.

3.2. Material characterisation

The influence of solvothermal treatment on the porous architecture of the dry active material powder was examined using N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherms, pore size distribution analysis, and specific surface area measurements. Both AC and TAC samples displayed type IV isotherms, indicative of their porous nature (Fig. 3a). Following thermal treatment, TAC demonstrated a higher specific surface area (2471 m^2

g^{-1}) compared to AC ($2040 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$). Additionally, the pore size analysis revealed an increase of approximately 50 % in average pore volume from $1.22 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$ to $1.83 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ g}^{-1}$ (Fig. 3b). Probe sonication induces cavitation, which disintegrates carbon agglomerates into smaller, evenly distributed particles, while also forming microcracks and edge defects. This process increases the external surface area and creates new pore channels. Following this, solvothermal treatment in DMF at $160 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 12 h encourages surface functionalisation through incorporation of oxygen-containing functional groups and structural rearrangement. DMF serves as both a solvent and a mild reducing agent, aiding in pore expansion. These combined effects improve surface area, porosity, and wettability, which are essential for applications like screen-printable inks. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was conducted to evaluate the thermal behaviour of AC and TAC (Fig. 3c). The weight loss profiles reveal distinct differences between the two materials. TAC exhibits a noticeable initial weight loss below $200 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, absent in the AC profile. This

Fig. 5. CV curves of (a) AC and (b) TAC recorded at various current densities, (c) comparison of AC and TAC at scan rate of 5 mV s^{-1} , and (d) plots of peak current vs. corresponding scan rate for AC and TAC, for determining the value of Cdl.

early-stage loss is attributed to the desorption of physically adsorbed DMF molecules, indicating their confinement within the porous structure of TAC. In the main decomposition stage ($500\text{--}700^\circ\text{C}$), both samples undergo substantial weight loss associated with carbon matrix degradation. However, TAC begins to degrade slightly earlier and reaches a lower residual weight than AC, suggesting reduced thermal stability, potentially due to physical interaction of less stable components within the matrix. Above 700°C , AC retains a higher residual mass compared to TAC, further supporting the conclusion that TAC contains more volatile species and has slightly lower thermal stability due to DMF adsorption and surface modification effects. The proton NMR spectra clearly indicate the entrapment of dimethylformamide (DMF) molecules within the pores and scaffold of the activated carbon. As shown in Fig. 3d, the spectrum of pristine activated carbon displays only the solvent peaks (DMSO-d_6). In contrast, the spectrum of the DMF-treated activated carbon (TAC) exhibits additional signals at 2.72 and 2.89 ppm (labelled A and A'), corresponding to the N-methyl groups of DMF, and a distinct peak at 7.95 ppm (B), attributed to the aldehydic proton of DMF. Furthermore, a downfield shift is observed in comparison to the free DMF signals: the N-methyl proton peaks shift from 2.97 to 2.88 ppm to 2.89 and 2.72 ppm, respectively, while the aldehyde proton shifts from 8.20 to 7.95 ppm. These chemical shift changes suggest physical interactions likely through van der Waals forces or hydrogen bonding between the DMF molecules and the activated carbon surface.

Fig. 4a presents the Raman spectra of AC and TAC. $I_{\text{D}}/I_{\text{G}}$ ratios for AC and TAC were determined to be 1.56 and 1.77, respectively, clearly indicating that TAC has a higher level of defects compared to AC. A

higher $I_{\text{D}}/I_{\text{G}}$ ratio signifies an increase in defect density or structural disorder within the carbon material. This implies that the solvothermal treatment introduced more defects, leading to greater disorder in the activated carbon. The FTIR spectrum shown in Fig. 4b exhibits a strong and sharp peak at approximately 1670 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the C=O stretching vibration. This distinctive feature of DMF clearly confirms the presence of the carbonyl group. In the TAC samples, this peak provides strong evidence for the adsorption of DMF molecules onto the AC surface [58]. The XRD pattern recorded is shown in Fig. 4c. In the patterns for AC and TAC, a pronounced increase in peak intensity is observed near $2\theta \approx 10^\circ$, suggesting the presence of numerous pores. This observation reflects a highly porous architecture, typical of materials with extensive surface area and complex pore networks [59]. The presence of broad diffraction peaks confirms that both samples possess an amorphous structure, while TAC exhibits a higher degree of crystallinity than AC around $2\theta \approx 45^\circ$, likely attributed to the effects of the solvothermal process. Furthermore, energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) elemental analysis on both pristine AC and TAC samples was performed. The measurements were conducted at 10 keV with a working distance of 8.3 mm. The obtained EDS spectra for both AC and TAC, along with elemental mapping results, are shown in Fig. 4d–i. The results clearly indicate a higher nitrogen content in TAC compared to AC. Specifically, the quantitative EDS analysis by Stoichiometry combined elements shows that the nitrogen content in TAC is 31.4 wt% (σ), while in AC it is 12.0 wt% (σ), confirming a significant increase in nitrogen after DMF treatment. This enhanced N content can be attributed to the introduction of nitrogen-containing functional groups during the DMF

Fig. 6. Two-electrode specific capacitance measured using (a) GCD at 0.15–1.5 A g⁻¹ (mean ± std dev, N = 6) and (b) CV at 5–100 mV s⁻¹. (c) GCD curves measured at 0.5 A g⁻¹, (d) CV curves measured at 10 mV s⁻¹.

modification process. The elemental mapping analysis shows a uniform distribution of nitrogen across the TAC surface, further confirming the successful incorporation of nitrogen functionalities. Fig. S3 in supplementary information shows the FESEM images of both pristine AC and TAC at three different magnifications. Overall, the FESEM images reveal no significant morphological differences between AC and TAC, suggesting that the treatment does not notably alter the surface structure. However, compared to AC, the TAC images reveal slightly larger and more irregularly shaped particles, indicating that the treatment may have induced some subtle changes in surface morphology and particle aggregation. Additionally, no significant differences were observed in the TEM images (Fig. S4 in supplementary information), which is consistent with the results obtained using FESEM.

3.3. Determination of electrochemically active surface area (ECSA) for AC and TAC using three-electrode system in aqueous electrolyte

The electrochemically active surface area (ECSA) reflects the true area of the electrode that contributes to electrochemical reactions, which often exceeds the apparent geometric area due to surface roughness or porosity. A larger ECSA translates to more accessible reaction sites, thereby enhancing charge storage capacity and improving overall capacitance. This also promotes efficient ion movement and electron transfer, minimising internal resistance and allowing for quicker charging and discharging. To estimate ECSA, CV was performed within a non-Faradaic potential window (0–1.0 V vs. Ag/AgCl) using scan rates ranging from 2 to 30 mV s⁻¹. Fig. 5a and b show the CV profiles of AC and TAC at these scan rates, while Fig. 5c compares both electrodes at 5 mV s⁻¹. TAC exhibits a significantly larger enclosed area, indicating superior charge storage capability. The double-layer capacitance (C_{dl}) was determined from the slope of the linear plot of peak

Table 2

Key electrochemical performance metrics of two-electrode SCs, with capacitance and ESR measured at current densities of 0.15 A g⁻¹ and 1.5 A g⁻¹, respectively. Sample size N = 6 for each device type.

Electrode		AC		TAC	
		NaCl	DES	NaCl	DES
Specific capacitance (F g ⁻¹)	minimum	11.0	14.8	27.2	28.1
	average	11.7	16.7	28.0	32.8
	maximum	12.2	18.0	28.6	36.8
ESR (Ω)	minimum	15.3	12.0	10.8	15.1
	average	16.7	13.4	11.3	16.7
	maximum	20.5	15.2	12.5	18.3
Energy density (Wh kg ⁻¹)	minimum	2.19	6.66	5.43	12.6
	average	2.35	7.48	5.60	14.8
	maximum	2.43	8.09	5.72	16.6
Power density (kW kg ⁻¹)	minimum	2.09	6.36	5.51	5.78
	average	2.46	7.89	5.79	6.76
	maximum	2.66	9.37	6.08	7.37
Specific leakage current (μA F ⁻¹)	minimum	33.8	133	28.0	103
	average	37.7	139	29.1	108
	maximum	40.4	145	30.4	113

current versus scan rate (Fig. 5d and Fig. S5 in supplementary information) at 2–20 mV s⁻¹, and the ECSA was calculated by dividing C_{dl} by the specific capacitance (C_s), typically 40 μF cm⁻² in aqueous systems [60]. Based on this analysis, the ECSA of TAC is approximately 4.4 times as high as that of AC (6087 cm² vs. 1388 cm²). The notably lower ECSA of AC suggests that the addition of drying retardant limits the exposure of electrochemically active sites, thereby restricting charge transfer and reducing overall electrochemical performance.

Fig. 7. (a) Ragone plot of specific energy vs. specific power measured using CV at 5–100 mV s⁻¹, including comparative literature references from Ref. [62] (A and B) [43], (C) [63], (D) [64], (E), and [65] (F). (b) Capacitance retention during the first 10,000 charge-discharge cycles at 1.5 A g⁻¹, measured using GCD at 0.15 A g⁻¹. (c) Nyquist plot of impedance spectra measured using EIS at 0.01–1,000,000 Hz, before (solid) and after (dotted) 10,000 GCD cycles. (d) Bode plot of measured phase angles before cycling, and modified Randles circuit used for EIS analysis.

3.4. Electrochemical performance of symmetric two-electrode supercapacitors

Fig. 6a and b illustrate the gravimetric specific capacitance measured for symmetric two-electrode SCs with AC and TAC electrodes. Notably, TAC demonstrates a specific capacitance increase of ~140 % with aqueous electrolyte, and an increase of ~80 % with DES, compared to AC. The specific capacitance of TAC is enhanced by the absence of drying retardant in the ink mixture, which limits the ECSA of the non-treated AC electrodes. The excellent energy storage capabilities of the DES electrolyte are best demonstrated at relatively low charge/discharge rates, where it exhibits a significant increase in specific capacitance; the average specific capacitance measured at 0.15 A g⁻¹ current density is approximately 5 F g⁻¹ higher with the DES electrolyte compared to NaCl, as shown in Table 2. Correspondingly, the energy density obtained with DES is ~120 % and ~220 % higher at 0.15 A g⁻¹, with AC and TAC, respectively. However, the high viscosity of the DES electrolyte significantly restricts the movement of ions when the charge/discharge rate is increased, limiting the capacitance obtained from the narrowest pores of the carbon matrix. This causes the observed decrease in specific capacitance with increased current density or scan rate. This behaviour is more pronounced with TAC compared to AC, implying that the drying retardant used in the AC ink mainly blocks the smallest pores of the carbon matrix, while still allowing ions to access the wider pores, the capacitance of which is not as rate dependent. The GCD and CV plots in Fig. 6c and d show typical EDLC behaviour, i.e. linear and symmetric voltage responses, and quasi-rectangular voltammograms with no obvious redox peaks, indicating that the solvothermal treatment does not induce significant pseudocapacitive effects to the TAC material, and the increase in specific capacitance is merely a result of increased double

Table 3

Fitted equivalent circuit parameters before and after 10,000 charge-discharge cycles.

	Device	L _s (nH)	R _s (Ω)	C _{EDL} (μF)	σ _{ZW} (Ω s ^{0.5})	R _{CT} (Ω)	C _s (mF)
Before 10,000 cycles	TAC + DES	181	13.9	18.6	2.30	1.84	197
	TAC + NaCl	114	11.3	5.08	0.471	0.579	161
	AC + DES	121	12.3	9.32	2.10	1.13	93.3
	AC + NaCl	118	14.7	4.90	1.32	0.824	104
After 10,000 cycles	TAC + DES	112	13.5	24.7	6.61	2.34	224
	TAC + NaCl	148	9.37	4.87	0.574	0.567	165
	AC + DES	203	11.4	11.9	2.30	1.20	93.0
	AC + NaCl	112	10.6	5.23	1.15	0.775	105

layer capacitance. In addition to not obstructing the microporous carbon matrix, the solvothermal treatment on the contrary expands the porous structure of active material, further increasing the ECSA and specific capacitance of TAC, compared to non-treated AC. Fig. 7a shows a Ragone plot illustrating the gravimetric specific energy vs. specific power measured at 5–100 mV s⁻¹ scan rates, in comparison with recently reported printed SCs. The areal energy vs. power densities of the devices measured using GCD at 0.3–3 mA cm⁻² are presented in Fig. S6 of supplementary information. Notably, screen-printed TAC

demonstrates high electrochemical performance compared to other state-of-the-art printed SCs [61] due to its enhanced thick film deposition and ECSA. Furthermore, as illustrated in Fig. 7b, no significant degradation in capacitance retention performance after 10,000 cycles is observed with TAC compared to non-treated AC, supporting the viability of the solvothermal approach for fabricating printed EDLCs.

EIS measurements were carried out before and after cycling the SCs for 10,000 charge-discharge cycles at 1.5 A g^{-1} to evaluate their internal resistance and diffusion behaviour. Nyquist and Bode plots obtained from the EIS measurements are presented in Fig. 7c and d, respectively. All devices demonstrate near-ideal capacitive behaviour at low frequencies, with vertical lines in the Nyquist plot and phase angles approaching -90° . In the high frequency region of the Nyquist plot, small semicircles typical of practical SCs can be observed [57,66]. A modified Randles circuit (insert in Fig. 7d) was used to fit the experimental data and obtain the circuit parameters presented in Table 3. Notably, the ESR of the devices is dominated by the series resistance R_S , which represents the combined ohmic resistance of the electrolyte, electrodes, and current collectors. Due to the small thickness ($\sim 20 \mu\text{m}$) of the electrode and electrolyte layers in the stacked SC structure, their contribution to the value of R_S is relatively small, and the majority of ESR comes from the high ohmic resistance of the graphite current collectors. All SCs demonstrate small charge transfer resistance (R_{CT}) values in the order of $1\text{--}2 \Omega$, with no substantial increase after 10,000 galvanostatic cycles, indicating efficient charge transfer at the electrode-electrolyte interface. Warburg impedance Z_W , which characterises the diffusion behaviour of ions within the porous electrodes, is observed as a sloped low-frequency section in the Nyquist plot. The DES-based devices exhibit higher Warburg coefficient (σ_{ZW}) values indicative of more sluggish ion diffusion compared to NaCl, which is expected due to the higher viscosity of the electrolyte medium. A notable increase in σ_{ZW} after 10,000 charge-discharge cycles is observed with TAC + DES ($2.30 \Omega \text{ s}^{0.5}\text{--}6.61 \Omega \text{ s}^{0.5}$), which can result from increased electrolyte penetration into the fine porous structure of TAC and consequently longer diffusion pathways, or changes in electrode morphology due to continuous ion adsorption and desorption during cycling.

4. Conclusions

Solvothermal treatment at 160°C for 12 h substantially improves the screen-printability of the YP-80F activated carbon in aqueous medium, due to the incorporation of DMF within the active material enhancing the stability and wettability of the water-based ink. In TGA, the initial weight loss of TAC below 200°C confirms DMF adsorption within the activated carbon matrix, as this behaviour is absent in AC. TAC also shows slightly reduced thermal stability in TGA, indicated by earlier decomposition due to the adsorbed DMF molecules in the AC matrix. The chemical shift changes in the proton NMR spectra confirm that DMF molecules are physically interacting with the activated carbon surface, indicating effective adsorption within the carbon matrix. The resulting improvement in printability allows the deposition of uniform electrodes without the need for an additional drying retardant solvent in the ink composition, which increases the specific capacitance of the electrodes by $\sim 80\text{--}140\%$ due to increased electrochemically active surface area and double layer formation. Other electrochemical performance metrics such as leakage current and cyclic stability are not negatively affected by the solvothermal process, making it a viable pre-treatment step for printed EDLC fabrication.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Aapo Kattainen: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Chirag Mevada:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Timo Punkari:** Writing – original draft,

Visualization. **Vijay Singh Parihar:** Writing – original draft, Investigation. **Hamed Pourkheirollah:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Investigation. **Jari Keskinen:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Matti Mäntysalo:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2025.238663>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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